

Promoting Ho Chi Minh City’s Leading Role and Its Capacity to Connect Regional Industrial Value Chains

Huynh Thanh Dien

Nguyen Tat Thanh University

thanhdien82@gmail.com

Abstract

Following the administrative expansion through the merger with Bình Dương and Bà Rịa–Vũng Tàu, Ho Chi Minh City has formed an integrated industrial space with superior capabilities within the Southern Key Economic Region. This article analyzes the city’s new role as the core coordinator of regional industrial value chains, clarifying the current distribution of industries, levels of specialization, and existing linkage–spillover mechanisms. The findings show that the merger of the three localities creates a foundation for integrated value chains, from R&D, design, and production to logistics and export—while enabling each province to shift from standalone development to functional specialization within a shared ecosystem. Based on this, the article proposes a model for organizing integrated production space, inter-regional coordination mechanisms, infrastructure connectivity development, and enterprise support. Ho Chi Minh City should transition from a localized growth center to a regional nucleus and diffusion axis, leading production assignment, logistics, and R&D for the entire region. Priority actions include establishing a regional coordination institution, investing in strategic infrastructure, connecting supply chains, strengthening FDI–domestic enterprise linkages, and developing satellite R&D networks. The study provides theoretical and practical foundations for a regional industrial development model oriented toward integration, coordination, and sustainability.

Keywords: Regional industrial value chains; spatial linkage; institutional coordination; industrial development; Ho Chi Minh City; Southern Key Economic Region.

1. Introduction

In the process of accelerating industrialization alongside deeper international economic integration, regional linkages and the spatial reorganization of production value chains have become a dominant trend in many countries. In Vietnam, the Southern Key Economic Region—with Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC) as its core—has played a leading role in national economic growth for the past three decades. Particularly in the context of large-scale administrative reforms, the administrative merger of HCMC with neighboring localities such as Bình Dương, Đồng Nai, and Bà Rịa–Vũng Tàu presents an opportunity to reshape the entire regional economic and industrial structure.

The merger of HCMC with Bình Dương and Bà Rịa–Vũng Tàu lays the groundwork for the development of an integrated industrial value chain encompassing R&D, design, production, logistics, and export. From this core linkage axis, growth dynamics are expected to diffuse across the entire Southeast region. The provinces can transition from fragmented development to functional specialization within a shared ecosystem: Đồng Nai as a center for supporting industries and high-tech manufacturing; Long An as a transitional industrial–agricultural zone connecting the Mekong Delta with the regional core; Tây Ninh as a frontier logistics and renewable energy hub; and Bình Phước as a material-processing and transit gateway linking to the Central Highlands. However, in practice, value-chain linkages among regional localities remain limited. There is still a lack of effective coordinating mechanisms, unclear functional division, insufficiently integrated regional logistics, and modest spillovers of technology, capital, and institutional capacity from HCMC.

In this context, a new perspective is needed, one that views HCMC not merely as a large metropolitan area but as a regional coordinating nucleus, leading the formation of integrated production networks, enhancing value added, and promoting balanced development across the Southern Key Economic Region. Clarifying the theoretical foundations, assessing the current state of regional industrial value-chain linkages, and proposing appropriate regional coordination and development solutions are crucial for shaping industrial policy in the new phase.

This article aims to: (i) analyze the role and potential of HCMC after the administrative merger in leading regional industrial value chains;; (ii) assess the current distribution of industries, linkage mechanisms, and the level of regional integration; and; (iii) propose a model for integrated, functionally specialized, and well-coordinated regional value-chain development.

In doing so, the study contributes institutional and spatial perspectives to regional development strategy and provides scientific foundations for establishing a more focused

and effective coordination mechanism for industrial value chains in Vietnam’s most dynamic economic zone.

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2. Theoretical Foundations and Analytical Framework

2.1. Theoretical Foundations

To analyze Ho Chi Minh City’s role in leading and coordinating regional industrial value chains, this study draws upon four main theoretical pillars: (i) value chain theory, (ii) growth pole theory, (iii) functional region and production network theory, and (iv) polycentric urban region theory.

First, Value Chain Theory, introduced by Porter (1985), posits that economic value is created through a sequence of interrelated activities ranging from input procurement to final output. In the context of globalized production, value chains have expanded beyond the firm level to become organizational models at regional and national scales (Gereffi & Fernandez-Stark, 2011). Within such systems, economic centers act as organizers, coordinators, standard-setters, and providers of chain-support services, commonly referred to as *lead firms* or *anchor hubs*. With its position as the region’s hub for finance, technology, and human capital, Ho Chi Minh City is well-positioned to serve as such an anchor, thereby guiding and upgrading industrial value chains across the Southeast region.

Second, Growth Pole Theory, developed by Perroux (1955), emphasizes the role of economic “poles” in driving regional development through *spread effects* and *backwash effects*. Growth poles are concentrations of leading industries and breakthrough production factors. Ho Chi Minh City can be regarded as a regional growth pole with the capacity to generate spillovers in industry, science and technology, logistics infrastructure, and policy toward satellite provinces such as Bình Dương, Đồng Nai, and Long An.

Third, Functional Region and Production Network Theory asserts that an efficient economic space should be organized into a network of core–satellite centers with clearly defined functional specializations (Scott & Storper, 2003). In such networks, central cities undertake decision-making, design, and innovation functions, while surrounding localities perform production, processing, and logistics functions. This perspective aligns with the spatial structure of the expanded HCMC region, where the city can act as a coordinating center for an integrated industrial region linked to specialized supply chains and industrial zones.

Fourth, the Polycentric Urban Region (PUR) Theory, developed by Hall and Pain (2006), argues that large metropolitan regions should adopt a polycentric development pattern rather than concentrating excessively on a single urban core. PUR models allow economic and industrial functions to be allocated across multiple specialized centers, interconnected through transport infrastructure, logistics networks, and regional coordination mechanisms. HCMC and adjacent industrial cities can therefore form an integrated urban–industrial region characterized by functional specialization among innovation centers, production centers, logistics hubs, and port–energy hubs.

Together, these theoretical pillars provide the foundation for positioning Ho Chi Minh City not merely as a production center but as the *organizing nucleus* of regional industrial value chains, shaping a model of integrated, polycentric industrial space with enhanced competitiveness and regional coordination.

2.2. Analytical Framework

Building upon the theoretical foundations outlined above, this study develops an analytical framework to examine Ho Chi Minh City’s role in leading and organizing regional industrial value-chain linkages. The framework integrates the extended value chain approach, growth pole theory, regional production network models, and the polycentric urban region perspective. From these, the following components and relationships are established as the basis for analysis:

(1) Functional capabilities of Ho Chi Minh City

HCMC is identified as a center with superior capacities in research and development (R&D), finance, logistics services, human resource training, and institutional coordination. These characteristics reflect those of a “lead node” within an extended value chain (Gereffi & Fernandez-Stark, 2011) and simultaneously align with the attributes of a “growth pole” as described by Perroux (1955).

(2) Structure of the regional industrial value chain

The study examines the spatial distribution of activities within the regional industrial value chain across localities in the Southern Key Economic Region, covering stages from R&D, production, and assembly to logistics and market access. Identifying spatial specialization among provinces helps clarify the potential for forming an integrated regional production network.

(3) Institutional and infrastructural linkages within the region

HCMC can only fulfill its role as a regional coordinator if effective mechanisms for interprovincial collaboration exist. This component analyzes factors such as intergovernmental coordination mechanisms, regional policy frameworks, transport–logistics infrastructure connectivity, and the presence (or absence) of regional coordinating institutions (Scott & Storper, 2003).

(4) Mechanisms of spillover and regional coordination

The study assesses HCMC’s capacity to generate *spread effects* in technology, capital, skills, production standards, and governance, benefiting neighboring provinces. It also evaluates the two-way interactions between HCMC and surrounding localities based on functional complementarity rather than zero-sum spatial competition.

Table 1. Analytical Components and Their Relevance to the Study

Analytical Component	Content	Relevance to Research Objectives
HCMC’s functional position within the region	Production resources, technological capabilities, R&D center, logistics, finance, training, regional administration	Basis for HCMC to act as the “coordinating nucleus”
Regional industrial value chain	Key industries (textiles, machinery, electronics, logistics...), spatial distribution of production	Assessment of current linkages and identification of regional gaps

Existing regional linkage mechanisms	Regional policies, infrastructure connectivity, interprovincial institutions, local coordination	Identification of barriers and potential for effective coordination led by HCMC
Spatial specialization patterns	Roles of HCMC and surrounding provinces in value-chain stages (R&D – production – logistics – market access)	Clarification of potential for an integrated production network
Spread vs. backwash effects	Spillovers of technology, capital, and governance from HCMC to the region	Measuring HCMC’s role as a regional “growth pole”

Source: Compiled by the author.

The analytical framework guides the selection of evaluation indicators, survey design, and policy analysis in subsequent sections of the study. Depending on the specific research direction, the model can be quantified using indicators such as supply-chain linkage density, the share of value added generated in HCMC relative to the region, and the degree of alignment between industrial zoning and regional infrastructure distribution.

Figure 2. Analytical Framework for the Leading Role

Source: Proposed by the Author

3. Research Methodology

This study adopts a synthesis of four main analytical approaches to clarify Ho Chi Minh City’s role in organizing and coordinating regional industrial production value

chains. First, the institutional–spatial approach enables an examination of HCMC as a regional institution that simultaneously performs governance functions and serves as the spatial development core of the Southern Key Economic Region. Second, the extended value chain approach frames HCMC as a lead node within an interregional production system, with the capacity to steer, upgrade, and allocate value added across industrial production chains. Third, the regional production network approach focuses on cooperative–competitive relationships among localities based on functional specialization, thereby highlighting the potential for spatial integration of regional industrial systems. Finally, the regional linkage policy approach assesses the presence and effectiveness of planning instruments, investment policies, and multilevel coordination mechanisms, which are essential for realizing HCMC’s leading role.

The study employs an interdisciplinary methodology, combining institutional–spatial analysis, extended value chain assessment, and regional production network analysis to elucidate HCMC’s leadership role in the industrial space of the expanded region. It uses qualitative analysis of planning documents, policy papers, and technical reports, while also evaluating spatial functional roles and identifying the position of each locality within key industrial value chains. Network analysis and spillover assessment are conducted using data on GRDP, FDI, technology, and labor. The study also incorporates case study evidence to draw policy implications for the model of integrated regional development.

4. Current Role of Ho Chi Minh City in the Industrial Production Value Chain of the Southeast Region

4.1. Functional Position of the Expanded Ho Chi Minh City within the Region

According to Decision No. 370/QĐ-TTg dated May 6, 2024, the Southeast Region is planned to become one of the country’s most dynamic and modern economic hubs, serving as a leading engine for socio-economic growth. With the strategic orientation of developing into a highly advanced industrial–service–urban region, spearheading innovation, digital transformation, and green growth, the Southeast is organized under a polycentric spatial model that ensures coherent connectivity across infrastructure, the economy, and institutions.

The Southeast Region hosts the largest concentration of industrial parks in Vietnam, in terms of number, land area, and operational efficiency. According to the Vietnam Real Estate Association (2024), the region has approximately 120 operating industrial parks, accounting for nearly half of all industrial parks nationwide. Đồng Nai leads with 32 parks, followed by Bình Dương with 31, Long An with 23, Ho Chi Minh City with 19, and Bà Rịa–Vũng Tàu with around 15.

These industrial parks not only have substantial scale but also exhibit high occupancy rates, averaging above 80%, and reaching up to 95% in key localities such as Bình Dương and Đồng Nai. The region is also the country’s strongest magnet for foreign direct investment (FDI), attracting nearly 60% of total FDI into industrial parks, thanks to its synchronized transport infrastructure and superior interprovincial connectivity.

With an expanding network of expressways, ring roads, seaports, and the under-construction Long Thành International Airport, the Southeast Region functions as Vietnam’s strategic industrial and logistics nucleus.

Figure 3. Industrial Park Area by Regions in Vietnam

Source: Calculations Based on Data from Provincial and Municipal Industrial Park

Management Authorities

Figure 4. Provinces with the Largest Number of Operating Industrial Parks in Vietnam

Source: Vietnam Real Estate Association (2024)

In the regional division of functions, Ho Chi Minh City serves as the overarching coordinating center, evolving into a multi-centric megacity with core roles in finance, commerce, logistics, innovation, education and training, and advanced industry. The city is positioned as the regional center for research and development, a major consumption hub, and a provider of high-quality services, with the capacity to generate spillover effects and reorganize regional value chains. Binh Duong functions as a high-technology manufacturing pole, pioneering smart industry models, integrated urban development, and modern logistics, while also serving as the northern innovation gateway of the Ho Chi Minh City metropolitan region. Ba Ria Vung Tau serves as the national hub for port-based industry and energy, with the Cai Mep Thi Vai port cluster oriented toward becoming an international transshipment hub, connecting East–West logistics corridors and supporting the development of environmentally friendly coastal industrial and urban zones.

The administrative merger of Ho Chi Minh City with major industrial provinces such as Binh Duong and Ba Ria Vung Tau has created an expanded urban and industrial region of exceptional scale. The new region covers more than 6,770 square kilometers, has a population of around 13.7 million people, and recorded total budget revenue of nearly 678 trillion Vietnamese dong in 2024, accounting for about 40 percent of national revenue. The combination of a financial and technology center in Ho Chi Minh City, a modern industrial production base in Binh Duong and Dong Nai, and a major port and energy gateway in Ba Ria Vung Tau creates an interregional economic structure with competitiveness surpassing

many concentrated urban models in Southeast Asia. In this configuration, Ho Chi Minh City is not only the geographical core but also the functional core, supported by a comprehensive and advanced economic and technical ecosystem.

The expanded Ho Chi Minh City region possesses multi-layered production resources, a high density of enterprises, specialized industrial parks, and a strong presence of multinational investors. This allows for large-scale and flexible production organized along value chains. At the same time, an interregional network for research and development is emerging, with numerous research institutes, technical universities, high-tech parks, and innovation centers in Thu Duc, District 9, and Binh Duong playing central roles in design, testing, and product development for high-technology industries.

In addition, strategic logistics infrastructure is a key pillar of the region. The combined system of Cat Lai and Cai Mep Thi Vai seaports, Tan Son Nhat International Airport, regional ring roads, and expressways positions Ho Chi Minh City as the largest freight gateway in the South. The city is also the leading financial and industrial support services hub, hosting most financial institutions, auditing firms, legal service providers, and logistics companies that underpin regional industrial development.

A major advantage of the region is its large pool of technically skilled labor, supported by extensive training systems capable of supplying high-quality workers for technology-intensive and export-oriented industries. Importantly, the establishment of a regional coordinating authority following the administrative merger helps reduce institutional fragmentation, strengthen planning capacity, improve resource allocation, and enhance the implementation of cross-provincial development programs.

This strategic concentration and layering of functions provide the foundation for Ho Chi Minh City not only to act as a production center but also to become the organizing nucleus of regional industrial value chains. Through expanded spatial specialization, integrated infrastructure, and the diffusion of technological, institutional, and innovation standards, the expanded region is positioned to become Vietnam’s leading economic zone and a major hub of international integration.

Table 2. Strategic Functional Characteristics of the Expanded Ho Chi Minh City Region

Content	Key Features
Regional orientation	Leading center of economy, industry, and services; pioneer in innovation, digitalization, and green transformation.
Spatial organization	Polycentric model with integrated infrastructure, institutions, and economic systems.

Ho Chi Minh City	Financial center; R&D hub; logistics and training center; regional coordinating and spillover nucleus.
Binh Duong	High-tech manufacturing pole; smart industry; northern innovation subregion.
Ba Ria Vung Tau	Seaport and energy center; coastal logistics and clean industry.
Scale after merger	Area of 6,770 sq km; population of 13.7 million; budget revenue of approximately VND 678 trillion (2024).
Regional linkage structure	HCMC (services and R&D) + Binh Duong/Dong Nai (production) + Ba Ria Vung Tau (export and energy).
Regional advantages	Dense network of enterprises, industrial parks, and FDI; strong R&D; region-wide logistics connectivity.
Coordinating institutions	Formation of interregional institutions; reduced fragmentation; enhanced coordination capacity.

Source: Compiled by the author.

4.2. Current Status of the Regional Industrial Value Chain

The expanded Ho Chi Minh City region — comprising Ho Chi Minh City, Binh Duong, Dong Nai, Long An, and Ba Ria Vung Tau — is forming a diversified industrial value chain, with prominent sectors including textiles and garments, mechanical engineering, electronics, food processing, and logistics. However, the level of value chain integration remains limited. Regional development still tends to proceed in parallel or in competition for space among provinces, rather than through specialized functional division along value chain stages.

Structure of key industrial sectors in the region

Within the industrial space of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City region, each locality assumes a specialized role in the production value chain, forming a functional division that is complementary rather than competitive. Ho Chi Minh City focuses on sectors with high technological and service content such as electronics, precision engineering, and pharmaceuticals, while also serving as the center for research and development, logistics, and financial services that support industrial activities. Many high technology zones and industrial zones in Thu Duc, Cu Chi, and Nha Be are gradually transitioning toward technology and innovation oriented activities.

Binh Duong and Dong Nai act as the region’s two primary production poles, specializing in industries such as textiles, wood processing, mechanical components, plastics,

chemicals, and electronics. Binh Duong is well known for its integrated industrial urban service model represented by projects such as VSIP and Becamex, while Dong Nai is a major center for component production and export oriented goods with strong connections to both domestic and international markets.

Long An functions as a bridge between Ho Chi Minh City and the Mekong Delta, with strengths in food processing, beverages, packaging, plastics, and several supporting industries including light engineering and garments. Ba Ria Vung Tau serves as the logistics and energy hub of the region, anchored by the deep sea port system of Cai Mep Thi Vai and industrial zones dedicated to oil and gas, fertilizers, chemicals, and heavy industry, forming the foundation for large scale export and energy supply chains.

Level of value chain integration

Despite strong and diverse industrial capacities across the region, the level of value chain integration remains limited due to structural and institutional factors. First, there is no clear functional division among provinces within each industrial chain. For example, both Ho Chi Minh City and Binh Duong develop electronics manufacturing, but lack deep coordination in stages such as design, assembly, testing, and distribution, resulting in inefficient value chain operation. Additionally, regional logistics infrastructure is not fully integrated, creating disconnections between inland industrial zones in Binh Duong and Dong Nai and seaport systems in Ba Ria Vung Tau. This increases transit time, raises logistics costs, and reduces the competitiveness of the entire chain.

Shared regional infrastructure such as testing centers, technical standard platforms, research and development services, and interprovincial supporting industries has also not been established. This leads to weak linkages between foreign invested enterprises and domestic firms. Furthermore, competition among provinces in attracting investment, rather than strategic cooperation, has resulted in overlapping industrial structures, fragmentation of resources, and the breakdown of continuity within regional industrial planning.

Regional linkage gaps

At present, the expanded Ho Chi Minh City region has not yet formed an integrated production ecosystem for its key industrial sectors. The absence of a coordinating authority and functional spatial planning at the regional level has caused localities to operate as separate entities rather than as complementary components of a unified value chain. Linkages among enterprises also remain weak, particularly between domestic and foreign invested firms and between large corporations and small and medium sized enterprises. This significantly weakens endogenous capacity and the potential for upgrading regional industrial value chains.

Moreover, shared logistics infrastructure and seamless connectivity have not been established. The region lacks regional distribution centers, bonded warehouse networks, and dedicated rail corridors directly connecting industrial zones with seaports. Although the expanded region possesses sufficient scale, technological capability, and market demand to organize integrated industrial value chains, existing linkages remain fragmented, localized, and constrained by the absence of a regional coordination mechanism. As a result, the central coordinating role of Ho Chi Minh City has not been fully realized, and spatial linkages, logistics infrastructure, and regional institutions remain the major barriers to reorganizing industrial value chains toward higher efficiency and added value.

Table 3. Industrial Value Chain Linkages in the Expanded Ho Chi Minh City Region

Locality	Major Sectors	Industrial	Role in the Value Chain	Current Limitations
Ho Chi Minh City	Electronics, precision engineering, pharmaceuticals, research and development, logistics, finance		Center for research and development, testing, design, standard setting, market services, and logistics	Overlaps in industrial structure with Binh Duong, limited ability to coordinate the full chain, reliance on foreign investment
Binh Duong	Textiles, wood processing, mechanical engineering, plastics, chemicals, electronics		Major production pole, supplier of components and export goods	Parallel development with Ho Chi Minh City, lack of functional division along the chain
Dong Nai	Electronic components, food processing, rubber, chemicals		Supporting production, origin point for export goods	Weak logistics connection with ports, limited participation in research and development and design
Long An	Food processing, beverages, packaging, plastics, light engineering		Transitional zone, supplementing food and supporting industries	Unclear functional role in the value chain, weak and fragmented linkages

Ba Ria Vung Tau	Oil and gas, chemicals, fertilizers, heavy industry, port logistics	Export logistics, center for energy and deep sea port activities	Regional logistics connectivity remains inefficient, limited high technology value chain development
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Source: Compiled by the author.

4.3. Current Status of Regional Coordination Mechanisms

According to Decision 370/QĐ-TTg, the Southeast Region is oriented toward developing a modern transport system with strong linkages among Ho Chi Minh City, Binh Duong, Ba Ria Vung Tau, and surrounding provinces. In terms of road transport, key corridors include Ring Road 3, which connects Ho Chi Minh City with Binh Duong, Dong Nai, and Long An; Ring Road 4, which extends toward Tay Ninh and Binh Phuoc; and strategic expressways such as Ho Chi Minh City to Moc Bai, Ho Chi Minh City to Long Thanh to Dau Giay, Bien Hoa to Vung Tau, Ho Chi Minh City to Chon Thanh, Ben Luc to Long Thanh, and the coastal corridor from Ho Chi Minh City to the South Central Region. For rail transport, planned routes include Ho Chi Minh City to Can Tho, Thu Thiem to Long Thanh, Bien Hoa to Vung Tau, and the North South high speed railway. In aviation and maritime transport, development is centered on Long Thanh and Tan Son Nhat airports and the international transshipment port cluster of Cat Lai and Cai Mep Thi Vai. This interconnected transport system enhances connectivity with the Mekong Delta, the Central Highlands, the South Central Region, and international gateways such as Cambodia and Southern Laos.

Beyond transport infrastructure, the Southeast Region is oriented toward developing logistics centers in Ho Chi Minh City, Long Thanh, Ba Ria Vung Tau, and Binh Duong. These centers are linked with industrial zones, urban areas, and seaports along value chain stages, while also promoting investment in digital infrastructure and intelligent traffic management systems. In practice, however, the implementation of interregional projects faces significant constraints. Slow progress, lack of synchronization, and the absence of unified technical standards have caused many connectivity projects to be delayed or disrupted, reducing the effectiveness of regional linkages and industrial development.

From an institutional perspective, although a polycentric regional structure has begun to form, coordination mechanisms among provinces remain weak. Most major decisions are regulated by central authorities, while provinces lack a binding horizontal coordination mechanism. Current cooperation is largely voluntary, and there is no regional institution

with sufficient authority to approve, coordinate, and supervise cross provincial projects. Even though the expanded Ho Chi Minh City urban region gives the city the advantage to assume a central coordinating role, linkages with neighboring provinces remain primarily administrative and have not evolved into a substantive regional mechanism.

In terms of investment policy, although some provinces have proactively promoted public and private cooperation and administrative reform, the absence of a unified legal framework for the entire region means that these initiatives remain localized. The lack of mechanisms for sharing benefits, risks, and financial responsibilities among provinces represents a major barrier for large scale infrastructure projects, particularly in logistics and strategic transport. This highlights the urgent need for a strong regional coordination institution with clearly defined authority and appropriate financial mechanisms to promote unified and effective regional development.

Table 4. Barriers and Coordination Opportunities for Ho Chi Minh City

Existing Barriers	Coordination Opportunities for Ho Chi Minh City
Weak interregional mechanisms, absence of a strong coordinating institution at the provincial level	Ability to lead the establishment of the Ho Chi Minh City Regional Council with cross provincial decision making authority
Incomplete infrastructure and slow interregional projects due to limited budgets and lack of risk sharing policies	Ability to mobilize public and private capital and propose a regional investment fund to accelerate projects
Fragmented planning, risk of overlapping functional roles among provinces	Ability to develop a regional plan centered on Ho Chi Minh City to prevent dispersed investment
Absence of a benefit sharing framework, limited incentives for cooperation	Ability to promote the signing of an Inter provincial Agreement that allocates benefits among localities

Source: Compiled by the author.

Current regional linkage mechanisms remain largely spontaneous and lack a powerful regional coordinating institution. As a result, infrastructure development is inconsistent, policies are not aligned, and the formation of integrated regional value chains is delayed. With the expansion of the Ho Chi Minh City urban region, the city is well positioned to assume the role of a regional coordinating nucleus, provided that it proactively establishes

strong interregional mechanisms in terms of institutions, planning, finance, and benefit allocation. This would help transform potential into actual unified and efficient regional development.

4.4. Current Status of Spatial Specialization

In the context of the development of the Southern Key Economic Region and the expansion of the administrative and economic space of Ho Chi Minh City, spatial specialization is a critical factor for reorganizing industrial value chains in a more efficient and competitive manner. However, current conditions show that the functional division among provinces remains fragmented and lacks a strategic integrated orientation.

Relative Roles of Localities in the Regional Industrial Value Chain

Within the industrial value chain of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City region, localities are gradually forming a functional division that reflects their respective advantages. Ho Chi Minh City holds the central position in the chain, focusing on high value added stages such as research and development, design, testing, logistics, and market services. Research and development activities are concentrated in the Saigon High Tech Park, the Vietnam National University campus, and various specialized research institutes, serving as drivers of technological innovation. The city also hosts laboratories, testing centers, and technology advisory services that help standardize and improve product quality. With its large population and extensive commercial infrastructure, Ho Chi Minh City also serves as the region’s largest distribution, consumption, and logistics center.

As the two main production poles, Binh Duong and Dong Nai manage large scale manufacturing and processing stages in the chain. Binh Duong has strong development in mechanical engineering, electronics, garments, and wood processing, organized within modern industrial parks such as VSIP and My Phuoc. Dong Nai stands out in electronic components, food processing, rubber, and chemicals, playing a key role in supporting production and supplying components to major enterprises domestically and internationally.

As the region’s logistics and energy hub, Ba Ria Vung Tau provides essential transport and industrial inputs for heavy industries. The Cai Mep Thi Vai deep sea port system connects inland production zones with global export markets. The province is also home to energy, petrochemical, and fertilizer industries, which are central to heavy industry and export oriented value chains.

Long An, located adjacent to Ho Chi Minh City and directly connected with the Mekong Delta, functions as a transitional and supplementary production area in the chain. The province has strong activity in packaging, food processing, refrigeration products, and has

significant potential to support agricultural supply chains and food processing industries across the region.

Table 5. Roles of Localities in the Regional Industrial Value Chain

Locality	Role in the Value Chain	Key Functions
Ho Chi Minh City	Center for research and development, design, logistics, and market services	Concentrated research in SHTP, testing and standardization, large scale distribution
Binh Duong	Industrial production pole (mechanical engineering, electronics, garments, wood processing)	Modern industrial parks such as VSIP and My Phuoc, large scale manufacturing
Dong Nai	Supporting production and component manufacturing (electronics, food, chemicals)	Supplying components and supporting industries for major firms
Ba Ria Vung Tau	Port logistics and energy (deep sea ports, petrochemicals, fertilizers)	Export logistics through Cai Mep Thi Vai, supply of industrial energy and materials
Long An	Transitional and supplementary production area (packaging, food, refrigeration)	Linkage with the Mekong Delta, support for agricultural and food processing chains

Source: Compiled by the author.

Level of Specialization

Although the expanded Ho Chi Minh City region has begun to develop a functional distribution based on local advantages, spatial specialization remains spontaneous and lacks integrated planning. There is considerable overlap in industrial structures among Ho Chi Minh City, Binh Duong, and Dong Nai, particularly in electronics, mechanical engineering, and garments. This overlap reflects the absence of a regional level coordinating authority, resulting in provinces developing similar competitive industries rather than forming complementary segments of a unified value chain.

Furthermore, linkages between stages such as research and development, production, logistics, and market access are not yet spatially integrated. Many multinational corporations still organize their value chains through internal global networks, with limited connection to local production ecosystems. This weakens the formation of integrated

industrial clusters and reduces the spread of technology, standards, and managerial capabilities across the region.

Potential for Organizing an Integrated Production Network

Despite existing institutional and infrastructural barriers, the expanded Ho Chi Minh City region possesses significant potential to develop an integrated production network based on a tiered functional structure. In this structure, Ho Chi Minh City can serve as the central innovation node responsible for coordinating technological standards, research and development, logistics, and market functions. Surrounding provinces such as Binh Duong, Dong Nai, Long An, and Ba Ria Vung Tau can assume the roles of specialized production poles in heavy industry, light industry, and supporting industries, thereby forming a mutually reinforcing configuration across the value chain.

In particular, the regional infrastructure system, including Ring Road 3, Ring Road 4, the Bien Hoa to Vung Tau expressway, the Thu Thiem to Long Thanh railway, and port to industrial zone connectors, once completed, will considerably reduce logistics costs, shorten trading times, and enhance the efficiency of connectivity among production functions across the region.

If planned according to the principles of functional specialization, value chain integration, and centralized coordination, this production network can lay the foundation for a more synchronized and efficient regional industrial value chain. It would strengthen endogenous capacity, enhance technological autonomy, and reduce dependence on fragile global supply chains, thereby improving resilience and strategic competitiveness in the context of deep international economic integration.

4.5. Current Status of Spillover and Backwash Mechanisms: Assessing the Growth Pole Role of Ho Chi Minh City

Growth pole theory (Perroux, 1955) indicates that economic centers generate two simultaneous effects on surrounding areas: (i) **Spread effects**, which stimulate development through technology diffusion, capital flows, labor mobility, and institutional influence; and; (ii) **Backwash effects**, which reflect the tendency of the center to attract resources, investment, and human capital from neighboring localities. An assessment of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City region shows that both effects occur concurrently, although positive spillover remains limited relative to potential.

Spread Effects: Development Dynamics from Ho Chi Minh City to Surrounding Provinces

As the leading center for technology, finance, and logistics in Vietnam, Ho Chi Minh City has gradually generated positive spillover effects across the region.

In technology, research and development cooperation, technical training programs, and projects in the Saigon High Tech Park have enabled firms in Binh Duong and Dong Nai to access modern production processes and international standards, thereby improving production capability and product quality.

In finance, major credit institutions, banks, and investment funds headquartered in Ho Chi Minh City have expanded services to key industrial parks such as My Phuoc in Binh Duong, Amata in Dong Nai, and Phu My in Ba Ria Vung Tau, facilitating access to capital, credit guarantees, and financial services for manufacturing firms.

In institutions, Ho Chi Minh City has been a pioneer in digital government initiatives, smart urban services, and advanced public administration models. These experiences have become templates for surrounding provinces to adopt, thereby improving the business environment and accelerating modernization of urban and industrial governance across the Southern Key Economic Region.

Backwash Effects: Resource Attraction Toward the Center

Alongside its spillover role, Ho Chi Minh City also exhibits strong characteristics of a resource absorbing center. A key example is the continuous inflow of high skill labor. Most graduates, engineers, and skilled professionals from surrounding provinces choose Ho Chi Minh City as their long term workplace and residence, creating labor shortages in their home provinces.

In addition, business support services such as legal consulting, testing, logistics, and finance remain concentrated in Ho Chi Minh City. Firms in Binh Duong, Dong Nai, and Long An must rely on service providers headquartered in the city, increasing transaction costs and limiting the development of local support ecosystems.

Moreover, foreign investors often locate their headquarters or operating centers in Ho Chi Minh City, while assigning lower value added production tasks to neighboring provinces. This limits opportunities for technology absorption and managerial upgrading in those provinces, potentially widening regional development gaps and weakening the formation of an integrated industrial value chain.

Assessing the Growth Pole Role of Ho Chi Minh City

Despite the simultaneous presence of spillover and backwash effects, Ho Chi Minh City remains the most prominent growth pole of the Southeast Region. This is evident through several key indicators.

First, in economic scale, Ho Chi Minh City contributes more than 23 percent of national GDP, surpassing the combined output of major industrial provinces such as Binh Duong, Dong Nai, and Ba Ria Vung Tau. The city also leads in foreign investment attraction in both the number of projects and registered capital.

Second, Ho Chi Minh City has the fastest pace of technological innovation in the country, with a vibrant startup ecosystem, innovation centers, and early implementation of digital transformation initiatives. This positions the city as both the source of new technological and institutional standards and the focal point for resource allocation across the region.

Potential Transition from a Resource Absorbing Center to a Regional Diffusion Hub

To strengthen its growth pole role and maximize spillover benefits, Ho Chi Minh City must shift from being a resource absorbing center toward becoming a regional diffusion hub. The core of this transition is the creation of a regional innovation ecosystem that links universities, research institutes, businesses, and provincial governments. Such a system would enable deeper technological cooperation and more effective knowledge transfer.

Ho Chi Minh City should also establish satellite logistics centers, research and development hubs, and technical support facilities in Binh Duong, Dong Nai, and Long An under its professional coordination. This would create a geographically distributed yet functionally connected regional network.

Additionally, the city must lead initiatives for coordinated investment in transport infrastructure, digital infrastructure, and interprovincial institutional frameworks. Reducing transaction costs, shortening transport times, improving data connectivity, and harmonizing regional policies would allow the industrial value chain to operate more efficiently and sustainably, with Ho Chi Minh City serving as the region’s nucleus for innovation, standards, and growth momentum.

5. Orientations and Solutions for Strengthening Ho Chi Minh City’s Leading Role and Regional Industrial Value Chain Integration

5.1. Orientations

Following its merger with major industrial localities such as Binh Duong and Ba Ria Vung Tau, the new Ho Chi Minh City is positioned as an integrated economic and industrial space with a clearly enhanced regional leadership capacity. To fully realize this central role, the city needs to shift its development model toward an approach based on coordination, diffusion, and integration, rather than focusing solely on localized growth.

First, regarding functional space, the core area of Ho Chi Minh City should serve as the center for research and development, quality testing, financial services, logistics, and regional industrial policy coordination. Binh Duong (within the Ho Chi Minh City region) and Dong Nai should continue developing as high technology and supporting industry poles, specializing in sectors such as precision engineering, electronics, smart textiles, and deep processing. Ba Ria Vung Tau (within the Ho Chi Minh City region) should maintain its role as the import and export gateway, as well as the center for energy, petrochemicals, seaports, and specialized logistics. Long An should become the region for food processing, packaging, agricultural products, and transshipment between the Mekong Delta and the major consumption market of Ho Chi Minh City. Tay Ninh can develop renewable energy industries, energy equipment manufacturing, border logistics, and ecological industrial zones along the Moc Bai corridor. Binh Phuoc should assume the function of material transshipment and the development of wood processing, rubber, agricultural processing, and North South logistics.

Second, a formal regional coordination mechanism must be established, with Ho Chi Minh City serving as the lead institution responsible for guiding strategic orientation and ensuring substantive linkages among Southeast provinces. The establishment of a Southeast Region Development Council could be considered to coordinate regional planning and joint project implementation. This mechanism would not diminish local autonomy but instead provide a unified platform for cooperation, minimize planning conflicts, optimize resource allocation, and improve investment efficiency.

Third, in terms of infrastructure connectivity, Ho Chi Minh City should lead investment efforts into strategic transport corridors such as Ring Road 3 and Ring Road 4, the Thu Thiem to Long Thanh railway, regional logistics hubs, and inland container depots that connect seaports with industrial zones. At the same time, digital infrastructure, data systems, and soft logistics should also be developed to establish an intelligent trading network and increase transparency in supply chain operations.

Fourth, concerning enterprise development and supply chain enhancement, Ho Chi Minh City should implement policies that support domestic firms in deeper participation in industrial value chains. This includes establishing a regional supporting industry center, strengthening linkages between foreign invested enterprises and small and medium sized enterprises, and developing a regional standard system for technology, environment, and governance. The establishment of satellite research and development centers in Binh Duong and Dong Nai under the technical coordination of Ho Chi Minh City would contribute significantly to the diffusion of knowledge and innovation across the entire region.

Finally, regarding the institutional framework for development, the new Ho Chi Minh City needs to cultivate a regional governance model based on voluntary cooperation but supported by binding mechanisms related to shared benefits and shared responsibilities. Close collaboration among governments, enterprises, and financial and technological institutions will be essential to ensure that regional industrial value chains operate efficiently and enhance competitiveness within global supply networks.

5.2. Solutions

To realize the orientation of becoming the coordinating nucleus and leading force of the regional industrial value chain, Ho Chi Minh City must implement a comprehensive set of solutions across five key pillars.

First, regarding integrated production spatial planning, Ho Chi Minh City should lead the development of a regional industrial value chain map that clearly identifies the functional roles of each locality and the strategic nodes within the production network. On this basis, industrial zone planning should be adjusted toward specialized subregions, with Ho Chi Minh City focusing on high technology and innovation industries, Binh Duong and Dong Nai serving as centers of specialized large scale production, and Long An and Ba Ria Vung Tau developing supporting industries and export oriented logistics. The functional division by sector — such as electronics, engineering, pharmaceuticals, and food processing — will be the foundation for establishing closed and mutually reinforcing industrial chains.

Second, with regard to institutional coordination and regional linkage policies, a formal coordinating mechanism with legal authority and clearly defined powers is needed. This mechanism should enable joint planning, cross provincial budget allocation, and the approval of strategic interregional projects. At the same time, a regional standard system applicable to all industrial zones should be developed, including standards for infrastructure, environment, governance, and technology. Establishing a benefit sharing framework and binding responsibilities among localities will create a stable foundation for long term cooperation.

Third, in terms of infrastructure connectivity, Ho Chi Minh City should play a central role in implementing strategic transport projects such as Ring Road 3, Ring Road 4, the Bien Hoa to Vung Tau expressway, and the Thu Thiem to Long Thanh railway. In parallel, an integrated logistics system should be developed, including regional distribution centers, inland container depots, smart warehouses, and digital logistics platforms. This will reduce operational costs and enhance the competitiveness of the entire value chain. Digital infrastructure should also be treated as a strategic asset, enabling production data sharing and supply chain monitoring.

Fourth, regarding the development of domestic supply chains, Ho Chi Minh City should strengthen support for small and medium sized enterprises through supply and demand matching programs, technical training, and technology advisory services. The establishment of supporting industry centers and satellite research and development hubs in surrounding provinces will help diffuse innovation from Ho Chi Minh City to the region, while enabling local firms to increasingly participate in global value chains.

Finally, in terms of human resources and development governance, a regional scale network linking universities, research institutes, and enterprises should be promoted to train labor forces tailored to the needs of specific industrial chains. Establishing mechanisms for data sharing and cross sector policy coordination will improve governance efficiency. In addition, communication on regional development strategies should be strengthened to raise awareness, build social consensus, and foster cooperation among local governments, enterprises, and intermediary organizations.

Effective implementation of these solution groups will not only enhance the leadership role of the new Ho Chi Minh City but also provide the foundation for building an integrated, dynamic, and sustainable industrial space for the entire Southern Key Economic Region.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1. Conclusion

Following its merger with major industrial localities such as Binh Duong and Ba Ria Vung Tau, Ho Chi Minh City has not only expanded in geographic scale and population but has also redefined its role as a multifunctional industrial center of the Southeast Region. With its outstanding advantages in research and development infrastructure, logistics, finance, human resource training, and market connectivity, the city possesses all necessary conditions to shift from a single growth pole to the coordinating nucleus of the regional industrial value chain.

However, realizing this role requires addressing several core challenges, including the duplication of functional roles across provinces, the absence of an effective regional coordination mechanism, weak and fragmented value chain linkages, and insufficiently integrated logistics infrastructure. In this context, Ho Chi Minh City’s development orientation should focus on three priorities: restructuring production space toward functional specialization; establishing a legally empowered regional institutional mechanism; and investing in both physical and digital infrastructure to build an integrated, efficient, and flexible production network.

The success of the “Greater Ho Chi Minh City” model not only matters for the Southeast Region’s economic growth but also forms a critical foundation for developing a regional

governance framework with strong coordination capacity. This is essential as Vietnam transitions toward an integrated, innovation-driven, and sustainable development model. As the regional leader, Ho Chi Minh City must continue to innovate institutionally, expand development space, and generate far-reaching spillovers, thereby reinforcing its role as an economic locomotive not only for the region but for the entire country.

6.2. Recommendations

For the Ho Chi Minh City Government

To establish itself as the coordinating nucleus of the regional industrial value chain, the new Ho Chi Minh City must proactively design a regional coordination institution with clear authority. This entity could take the form of a Southeast Regional Coordination Committee or a special metropolitan and polycentric administrative model empowered to undertake joint planning, approve interprovincial projects, and allocate cross-provincial budgets. Simultaneously, the city should prioritize the construction of a regional industrial value chain map, which will serve as the foundation for spatial planning and functional specialization across provinces.

Regarding chain-supporting infrastructure, Ho Chi Minh City should accelerate investment in regional logistics hubs, shared production and market data systems, and digital infrastructure platforms connecting major industrial zones. These components are essential for enhancing chain performance and reducing transaction costs across the region. Additionally, the city should expand programs linking foreign invested enterprises with domestic firms, develop supporting industry service centers, and strengthen training for high-skill technical labor tailored to the needs of specific industrial chains.

These initiatives will enable Ho Chi Minh City to maintain its role as the regional economic and industrial center while creating the foundation for balanced, efficient, and sustainable development across the Southern Key Economic Region.

For Provincial Governments in the Southern Key Economic Region

Local governments must proactively define their specialized roles within the regional industrial value chain, focusing on clear functional assignments such as core production, supporting industries, logistics, or consumer markets. This functional repositioning will reduce overlapping industrial structures and uncoordinated investment competition, while fostering a more efficient and mutually reinforcing production network.

Provinces should also work closely with Ho Chi Minh City to implement interregional infrastructure projects in transport, logistics, energy, and environmental management. At the same time, they need to propose and adopt cross-provincial policy instruments that support unified and coherent regional planning. Participation in the formulation and

implementation of regional standards for technology, environment, and governance is vital to facilitate seamless investment flows and production mobility.

Lastly, provinces should establish or participate in benefit sharing and responsibility sharing mechanisms, aiming toward balanced and harmonious development. Only through close and substantive cooperation among provinces can the region fully unleash its collective potential and enhance competitiveness in the context of deep global integration.

For the Business Community

Businesses, especially foreign invested enterprises and large domestic corporations — should take the initiative in expanding linkages with small and medium sized firms through subcontracting, technology transfer, standardization support, and workforce training. Such deep linkages not only strengthen the competitiveness of domestic supply chains but also promote technology diffusion and production upgrading across the region.

Enterprises should also actively engage in sectoral networks, industrial clusters, and regional value chain associations to improve market connections, share information, and enhance production coordination. Investing in technological upgrading, supply chain digitalization, and standardized management processes will help firms integrate more deeply into regional industrial value chains and meet the increasingly stringent requirements of global markets.

Furthermore, enterprises should collaborate with governments in developing data sharing systems, compliance monitoring frameworks, and sustainable development models. Active participation and cooperation from the business sector will be crucial for driving long term growth, ensuring social economic harmony, and maximizing spillover effects across the regional industrial space.

Coordinated collaboration among Ho Chi Minh City, regional provinces, and the business community will be the key to building an integrated, innovative, and globally competitive production space in the context of shifting global value chains.

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